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EFFECT OF PULSED ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD ON BACTERIAL ACTIVITY IN SYNTHETIC WASTEWATER

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ABSTRACT

The paper studies the effect of a pulsed electromagnetic field (PEMF) with a pulse repetition rate of 16 Hz, a pulse filling frequency of about 100 kHz and a magnetic induction of no more than 500 nT on the processes of glucose decomposition, nitrification and denitrification in synthetic wastewater and on the maximum dissolution of oxygen in this water. It is shown that this PEMF accelerates the process of aerobic decomposition of glucose by approximately 20%, which indicates a higher activity of ammonifiers. This PEMF also accelerates the process of aerobic nitrification by 25-30% and the process of anaerobic denitrification by approximately 20%. In addition, it is shown that this PEMF increases the maximum solubility of oxygen in tap and synthetic wastewater.

Keywords: ammonification, nitrification, denitrification, pulsed electromagnetic field, synthetic wastewater.

Introduction.

There are data in the literature on the stimulating effect of electromagnetic fields (EMF) on various microorganisms of activated sludge [1, 2].

Most of the reports are about the effect of static magnetic fields (SMF) on microorganisms of activated sludge. For example, in [3] it was shown that acceleration (by 44%) of the oxidation reaction of the glucose substrate in synthetic wastewater was observed at an SMF of 17.8 mT. It was also shown that an SMF of 5 mT increases the activity of aerobic ammonium-oxidizing bacteria by increasing the rate of free ammonia entering the microbial cells [2]. In [4] it was shown that at an ammonium nitrogen concentration of 50 mg/l in the control in the absence of a magnetic field, complete removal of nitrogen occurred in 10 hours, and in the presence of an SMF of 50 mT in 7 hours, i.e. 30% faster. In another work [5] it was shown that when treating the SMP with 88.0 mT of a mixture of wastewater and activated sludge, after 8 hours the concentration of COD was 19% lower than in the control, the concentration of ammonium nitrogen (NH₄-N) was 6% lower, the concentration of nitrites (NO₂) was 44% lower, phosphates (PO₄) was 35% lower relative to the control, and in general, the sedimentation of sludge was higher than in the control.

There is a work that shows that the metabolism, growth and reproduction of microorganisms in activated sludge are significantly enhanced after exposure to EMF with a frequency of 50 Hz and a strength of 4-6 V/m [6].

Unfortunately, static EMF and sinusoidal low-frequency EMF of 50 Hz do not spread further than 10-15 cm from the inductor, so the work is of interest, which showed that aerobic purification of a mixture of wastewater and activated sludge in the presence of a continuous pulsed electromagnetic field (PEMF) with a frequency of 16 Hz and a magnetic induction of no

more than 0.5 μ T accelerates the ammonification process by 25%, nitrification and denitrification by 15%, accelerates the reduction of COD by approximately 20%, increases the mass of activated sludge and the rate of its sedimentation. Since these PEMF can spread in water from the antenna for several meters, the authors suggest that with the help of these PEMF it is easy to accelerate the purification of wastewater in aeration tanks with a volume of several hundred cubic meters [7].

However, the question of what the mechanism of this action is and how these PEMF act on various groups of microorganisms of activated sludge remains unclear. To study the mechanism of action of PEMF on various groups of microorganisms, synthetic wastewater can be used, in which glucose and yeast extract are used as a substrate for ammonifiers, (NH₄)₂SO₄ for nitrifiers, and KNO₃ for denitrifiers.

In addition, there are contradictory data in the literature on the effect of EMF on the maximum solubility of oxygen in water. In some studies, the authors report that treating water with EMF increases the solubility of oxygen in it [8, 9], while in others they prove that it does not affect [10]. In these studies, the authors used static magnets, and the effect of PEMF on the maximum solubility of oxygen in water was not studied. Clarification of this issue is important, since an increase in the solubility of oxygen in water in the presence of PEMF can partially explain the mechanism of acceleration of wastewater treatment in the presence of PEMF.

The purpose of this work was to study the effect of PEMF on different groups of microorganisms and the solubility of oxygen in water in experiments with synthetic wastewater.

Materials and methods.

From the list of the most common synthetic wastewaters [11], the two simplest ones were selected. One was based on glucose (Glucose - 800 mg/l, NH₄Cl

-76 mg/l, KH₂PO₄ – 22 mg/l [12]), so that it would be possible to observe the activity of ammonifying bacteria that decompose glucose using a simple glucose analyzer (YSI Model 27, Ohio, USA), as described in [3]. In another (Acetic acid - 330 mg / l, NH₄Cl - 100 mg / l, K₂HPO₄ - 250 mg / l, KH₂PO₄ - 50 mg / l [13]), measuring the concentration of ammonium and nitrate ions using ion-selective electrodes Intellical ISENH4 181AP and Intellical ISENO3 181AP from Hach (Great Britain) using a pH meter F20-Standard from Mettler-Toledo GmbH. [14] it is possible to observe the activity of nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria.

Activated sludge obtained from one of the aeration stations of Tashkent (Uzbekistan) was adapted to a synthetic medium by incubating it in this medium on a shaker at a temperature of 30 ° C for 24 hours.

The experiment was conducted in two 3.0 l reactors, in which aeration and mixing were performed using an aquarium compressor with a sprayer. The reactors were located at a distance of 4 m from each other in one room, in which one temperature (about 24°C) was maintained using an air conditioner.

An electromagnetic pulse generator manufactured by Inter Trade Praha spol. s.r.o. (Czech Republic) was used in the work. A 1 m long antenna wire from the generator was wound around one of the reactors. The antenna emitted pulses with a repetition rate of 16 Hz, with a filling frequency of about 100 kHz and a magnetic induction of no more than 500 nT (monitored using a UHS-2 milligaussmeter from AlphaLab Inc

(USA), a Siglent SHS 810 digital oscilloscope (China) or a portable long-wave radio receiver). The pulse oscillogram is presented in [7]. No electromagnetic pulses were observed in the control reactor.

The dissolved oxygen concentration was measured using an oximeter with a Clark polarographic electrode, model JPB-70A (China). For the measurement, water was poured into a 500 ml beaker and an air diffuser with a tube from an aquarium pump and an oximeter were immersed in it. The generator antenna was placed around the beaker. When the oximeter reading stabilized, it was recorded. Then the pump was turned on and the stabilized oximeter reading was recorded when the water was saturated with air. Then the generator was turned on and the stabilized oximeter reading was recorded when the water was saturated with air and under the action of PEMF.

Results and discussion.

The concentration of dissolved oxygen in water depends on many factors: temperature, pressure, water pollution with mineral salts, organic compounds, oxygen-consuming microorganisms and oxygen-releasing photosynthetic microorganisms. The table presents the results of measuring the maximum solubility of oxygen in various waters at a temperature of 21°C with different water treatments. As can be seen from the table, treating water from various sources with a pulsed electromagnetic field with a frequency of 16 Hz increases the maximum solubility of oxygen in water.

Table.

Effect of a pulsed electromagnetic field (PEMF) on the maximum solubility of oxygen in some waters.

Water source	Maximum oxygen solubility, mg/l		
	Without air blowing	When blowing air	When blowing air and PEMF
Distilled water	6,7±0,2	8,8±0,2 (100%)	9,2±0,2 (104%)
Tap water	4,3±0,2	6,6±0,3 (100%)	8,0±0,1 (121%)
Synthetic wastewater with glucose and activated sludge	2,4±0,1	5,8±0,1 (100%)	7,3±0,1 (126%)
Synthetic wastewater with NH ₄ Cl and activated sludge	1,0±0,1	5,3±0,1 (100%)	7,0±0,1 (132%)

The figure shows the effects of pulsed electromagnetic field (EM) on the activity of ammonifying, nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria in synthetic wastewater in the presence of activated sludge.

From Figure 1 it is evident that the concentration of glucose in the synthetic wastewater with activated sludge in the presence of PEMF decreases by approximately 20% faster, which indicates a higher activity of ammonifiers.

From Figure 2 it is evident that the concentration of ammonium ions (NH₄) in the synthetic wastewater

with activated sludge in the presence of PEMF decreases by approximately 25% faster, which indicates a higher activity of nitrifiers.

From Figure 3 it is evident that the concentration of nitrates in the synthetic wastewater with activated sludge in the presence of PEMF increases by approximately 30% faster, which indicates a higher activity of nitrifiers.

From Figure 4 it is evident that denitrification occurs almost 2 times faster than ammonification and nitrification, and PEMF also accelerates this process by 20%.

Figure. Effect of pulsed electromagnetic field (EM) on the activity of ammonifying, nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria in synthetic wastewater in the presence of activated sludge. In Figures 1, 2 and 3, the medium was blown with air. In Figure 4, air was not blown. The results of one typical experiment of a series of 4 experiments are presented.

If ammonification and nitrification depend on the oxygen concentration in the environment and the acceleration of these processes can be partially explained by an increase in the solubility of oxygen in water in the presence of PEMF, then denitrification is an anaerobic process and an increase in the activity of denitrifiers can be explained by the direct effect of PEMF on the activity of these microorganisms.

Conclusion

Experiments with synthetic wastewater have shown that a pulsed electromagnetic field (PEMF) with a pulse repetition rate of 16 Hz, a pulse filling frequency of about 100 kHz and a magnetic induction of no more than 500 nT accelerates the process of aerobic decomposition of glucose by approximately 20%, accelerates the process of aerobic nitrification by 25-30% and the process of anaerobic denitrification by approximately 20%. In addition, it has been shown that this PEMF increases the maximum solubility of oxygen in tap and synthetic wastewater.

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